

EFFECTS OF ANNEALING TEMPERATURE ON THE GROWTH AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SnS:ZnS THIN FILMS

ABSTRACT

Thin film of SnS:ZnS has been deposited onto a glass substrate by Chemical bath deposition (CBD) technique at room temperature. Tin sulphate ($\text{SnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was the source of Sn while sodium thiosulphate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$) served as the source of Sn₂S. Ethylene Diamine Tetraacetic Acid (EDTA) was used as the complexing agent. The effect of variations in annealing temperature was studied. The optical and solid state properties of the film like Reflectance (R), Absorbance(A), Transmittance (T), Refractive Index (n), Extinction Coefficient (K), Refractive index (n), Absorbance Spectra (A), and Transmittance Spectra T (%) were determined. These properties make SnS suitable for solar cell fabrication, architectural design to reduce exposure to skin cancer, cataracts and impaired immune system due to UV rays. The band gap of the film (3.5eV) suggested that the material is a semiconducting thin film. In recommendation, this material has high transmittance and capable of absorbing UV rays, urgent development of this technology is recommended to lenses and mirror manufacturers.

Keyword: Thin film, temperature, EDTA, UV rays.

INTRODUCTION

Semiconducting metal chalcogenide nanoparticles have attracted research attention owing to their tunable absorption properties for photovoltaic and hydrogen production applications (Ali, 2015). In particular, there has been an increasing demand for tin sulfide (SnS) nanoparticles in recent years as photovoltaic materials, lithium battery anode materials, and photocatalytic materials owing to their favourable opt electrical properties, which can be easily altered by manipulating the synthesis conditions (Anthony and Murali, 2015). Until now, orthorhombic SnS was one of the most widely reported inorganic binary thin film solar cell materials, with a record efficiency (η) of 4.36% reported in 2014. For this, SnS was prepared by atomic layer deposition followed by subsequent annealing in an H₂S atmosphere, which enhances the production cost. In addition, the SnS thin film solar cell showed a low open-circuit voltage (VOC) of 0.372 V. In 2015, the polymorph of tin sulfide, chemically synthesized cubic SnS with a large band gap of ~1.7 eV, was reported. This cubic structure is identical to that of SnS nanoparticles or nanocrystals but can produce a higher VOC due to its wider bandgap property (Arandhara *et al.*, 2015). The polymorph of tin sulfide, SnS exhibited interesting characteristics such as a high absorption coefficient of 10⁴ cm⁻¹ in the

visible region, a direct optical bandgap of 1.7 eV, and a p-type conducting nature with dark conductivity of about 10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹, and had good photoconductivity response. In addition, both constituent elements of Sn and S are earth-abundant, inexpensive, and non-toxic. According to the literature, SnS has been explored for photocatalytic activity, but SnS was hardly studied despite of its promising characteristics (Bashar, 2020).

The properties of nanoparticles are highly dependent on the method of synthesis and preparative conditions such as precursor nature and concentration, synthesis temperature and time, solution pH, and the nature of the chelating agent. To exploit the novel properties of nanoparticles for a variety of applications, it is essential to tune the size, phase, structure, shape, and composition by optimizing the above-mentioned parameters (Bendjedidi, 2015). Zinc sulfide (ZnS) is one of the direct II–VI semiconductor compounds with large band gap energy of ~3.65 eV at room temperature¹. The material crystallizes in both cubic and hexagonal forms and is a material of reference to test several theoretical models in condensed matter physics (Altaf, 2015). Sometimes it shows mixed phase crystal structure. While cubic ZnS has been reported to have a wide direct bandgap of ~3.6 eV at 300K, hexagonal ZnS has been reported to have a bandgap of

~ 3.91 eV³. The material has huge potential application in both bulk and thin film form in various photovoltaic and optoelectronic devices (Elidriss, 2019). It is used as key material for solar control coating, optoelectronic devices, electroluminescence devices, sensors and others.

ZnS thin film is mostly suitable as a window layer in heterojunction photovoltaic solar cells; because the wide band gap reduces the window absorption losses and improves the short circuit current of the cell (Kumar *et al.*, 2015). Researches have shown that ZnS is transparent to visible light, opaque to ultraviolet radiation and near infra-red radiations (Osiele, 2017). ZnS materials could also be used in radio frequency field sputtered films such as CdZnS and modified ZnS/CdS (Oladeji and Chow 2015). Different techniques have been used to fabricate ZnS thin films, like sputtering (Shao *et al.*, 2013), molecular beam epitaxy (Kavanagh and Cameron 2011), spray pyrolysis (Elidrissi *et al.*, 2016), successive ionic layer adsorption and reaction technique (Nicolau 2018), pulsed-laser deposition (Yano *et al.*, 2013), chemical bath deposition (Fukarova-Juruskovska *et al.*, 2016), chemical vapour deposition (Kashani 2019), liquid phase atomic layer epitaxy (Lindroos *et al.*, 2014) and spin coating (Kumar *et al.*, 2015).

Among these, the spin coating techniques is an attractive method for thin film deposition for various reasons: it is less hazardous, less costly, progressively more uniform as it thins, fast operating system and thus capable of easy scaling up. Additionally, the growth of the films occurs at a relatively low temperature, compatible with flexible organic substrates (Berger *et al.*, 2017).

SIGNIFICANT OF THE STUDY

The effects of annealing temperature on growth and characterization of SnS:ZnS thin films is that most sulphide minerals do not allow the optimum recovery of metal by direct chemical leaching (Hiskey and

Wadsworth, 2016; Dutrizac, 2018), due to their low solubility in many leaching reagents. Therefore, for the metal content to be leached, the reagent must come into direct contact with metal atoms or metal containing compounds within the mineral ore. Amongst several methods, a suitable approach to ensure that the metal content of the ore comes in contact with the leachant, is to grind the ore fine enough to liberate all the mineral phases so as to enable them to be exposed to chemical attack. A limitation to grinding many sulphide ores is that the ore cannot practically be ground fine enough to expose the metals. For instance, chalcopyrite and sphalerite are frequently intergroup, with micro-size grains of 10-20 μm being dispersed within the pyrite (Gomez *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, due to these specific mineralogical characteristics, it is necessary to finely grind and concentrate the ore prior to the solubilisation of the valuable metals (Barbery *et al.*, 2018). Hence, this research work seek to understand the effects of annealing temperature on the growth and characterization of SnS:ZnS thin films.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This research is aimed at understanding the effects of annealing temperature on the growth and characterization of SnS:ZnS thin films. The research aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To study the optical properties and thickness of thin film growth.
2. Study the influence of applied techniques in determining the growth and characterization of SnS:ZnS thin films.
3. To identify possible areas of application

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The concern of this study is to understand the effects of annealing temperature on the growth and characterize SnS:ZnS thin film using chemical bath deposition technique and also to determine the optical and solid state properties of thin film such as

absorbance, transmittance, reflectance, absorption coefficient, band gap, etc and the film thickness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Semiconductor materials play an important role in our modern day electronics; including, transistors, diodes, integrated circuits and other solid-state devices. Such devices have been found to possess wide applications due to their numerous advantages such as compact sizes, reliability, power efficiency, and low cost. As discrete components, they have been found to be of use in power devices, optical sensors, and light emitters, including solid-state lasers. More importantly, they can be easily incorporated into the easily manufactural microelectronic circuits (Bernede *et al.*, 2019). They are, and will continue to be one of key elements for almost all electronic systems in the foreseeable future (Raskin, 2019). Thin films are crystalline or non-crystalline materials developed two dimensionally on a substrates surface by physical or chemical methods. They play a vital role in nearly all electronic and optical devices. They have been used as electroplated films for decoration and protection. They have long been used as antireflection coatings on window glass, video screens, camera lenses and other optical devices. These films are more than 100 nm thick, made from dielectric transparent materials and have refractive indices less than that of the substrate.

Tin Sulfide (SnS)

Over the past few decades, tin sulphide (SnS), deposited in the form of polycrystalline thin films, have been developed for use as absorber layer materials in photovoltaic solar cell devices. This has resulted in the production of commercial modules with efficiencies > 10 % for both technologies. In the case of SnS, the thin-film modules are now produced more cheaply than silicon-based modules (Cattell, 2017). There remains however concerns in some countries as to the desirability of using cadmium, a heavy

metal, in these devices. In the case of CIGS there are concerns with respect to the lack of availability of Ga and In, as this will limit the large-scale use of this product in the future. These drawbacks have led to research groups across the world investigating the potential of new materials that consist of elements that are both abundant and environmentally acceptable for use in such devices (Chaboti and Birouk, 2019). One of the many possible materials is tin sulphide, SnS. SnS has a near-optimum direct energy bandgap (1.35 eV), it is amphoteric, and it can be deposited by a wide range of chemical and physical deposition methods. To date the most commonly used methods for depositing SnS are chemical bath deposition, electrodeposition, spray pyrolysis and thermal evaporation.

In all these cases the photovoltaic effect has been observed and devices with efficiencies up to 2% produced using some of these methods (Choudapura, 2019). In this paper we have investigated the use of a less well investigated twostep process for making SnS, based on the use of sulphating thin films of tin that have been pre-deposited onto glass and Mo-coated glass substrates. In particular, the formation of SnS by annealing pre-deposited tin layers in a mixture of SnS, gas environment was investigated. The physical and chemical properties of the resulting films have also been compared with those obtained by annealing the tin layers in elemental sulphur (Dinsmore *et al.*, 2016). These routes for producing tin sulphide are compatible with existing industrial processes, as both the thin film deposition of tin layers and the sulphidisation processes are well established for other applications.

Zinc Sulfide (ZnS)

Zinc sulphide ZnS is one of the direct II–VI semiconductor compounds with large band gap energy of ~3.65 eV at room temperature (Rabah, 2019). The material crystallizes in both cubic and hexagonal

forms and is a material of reference to test several theoretical models in condensed matter physics. Sometimes it shows mixed phase crystal structure (Rabah *et al.*, 2019). While cubic ZnS has been reported to have a wide direct bandgap of ~ 3.6 eV at 300K, hexagonal ZnS has been reported to have a bandgap of ~ 3.91 eV³. The material has huge potential application in both bulk and thin film form in various photovoltaic and optoelectronic devices. It is used as key material for solar control coating, optoelectronic devices, electroluminescence devices, sensors and others (Cullis, 2017). ZnS is a prospective material to be used in solar cell as passivation layer for better photovoltaic properties⁶. Due to its high refractive index ($n \sim 2.3$), it can be used as an antireflective coating. ZnS is also an important phosphor host lattice material used in electroluminescent devices (ELD). This is because of its large band gap that is enough to emit visible light without absorption and the efficient transport of high energy electrons⁸. Various physical and chemical techniques have been used by researchers to deposit ZnS thin films (Addoua *et al.*, 2015). While physical deposition methods such as sputtering, metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD), molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) and atomic layer epitaxy (ALE) demand the use of either vacuum conditions and/or complex equipment, chemical techniques are simpler and cost effective. Thus they have become more popular in recent times. Various chemical techniques that has been used includes electrodeposition⁹, spray pyrolysis¹⁰⁻¹¹, sol-gel¹¹, spin coating⁵ and chemical bath deposition. The technique of CBD (also known as chemical solution deposition) is simple, inexpensive and can be adaptable to large area processing with low fabrication cost (Euchmuller, 2019). Also doping with metal ions at low temperatures can be conveniently carried out at this technique. Doping of ZnS with group II metal ions has been made to achieve improved electrical

and optical properties. Copper doping has been reported to strongly influence resistivity and band gap. Increase of Cu^{2+} concentration has been reported to result in quenching of luminescence due to formation of CuS (Sultana abd Siddika, 2020). Doping with Mn has been reported to give highly transparent ZnS film along with quantum size effect. Quantum confinement was also reported Mn doped ZnS thin films prepared by spin coating⁵. Strong luminescence band at energy 2.07 eV has been reported for Mn doped ZnS prepared by wet chemical technique. Doping of transition metal ions of copper and manganese has been reported to show intense, stable and tunable emission covering the blue to red end of visible spectrum (Berger *et al.*, 2017). As ZnS radiates luminescence with a wavelength 420-480 nm, copper and manganese has been doped to order to receive radiation in the visible region. Although influence of Cu and Mn on physical properties of ZnS has been reported by several researchers, influence of tin incorporation in ZnS thin film is almost non-existent.

For tin doped ZnS nanoparticles with thiourea as capping agent, quantum confinement effect leading to blue shift in band gap has been reported (Shankkar, 2016). Detail information regarding effect of tin incorporation on microstructure of ZnS is not available. This was the key motivation behind this work. In the present study we report the synthesis of ALS and ZnS thin films by dual solution.

Structure and properties of ZnS

Zinc sulphide (ZnS) is a highly important semiconductor material which belongs to the group of II–VI wide band gap semiconductors. In nature, ZnS is a white-to yellow-coloured powder or crystal. It exists in two crystallographic forms having cubic (sphalerite or zinc blende) or hexagonal (quartzite) crystal structure as show in Fig. (2.1). The hexagonal form is a thermodynamically metastable phase, which is usually stable at very high temperature, while the cubic form is more

thermodynamically stable phase at low temperature (Weller, 2019). ZnS has a direct transition type band structure. The cubic form has a band gap of 3.54-3.6 eV, whereas the band gap of hexagonal form is the highest being 3.74-3.87 eV. ZnS exhibits high transparency over the wide spectrum region between 380 nm and 25 μm . (Gafui *et al.*, 2020). The electrical resistivity is in the order of 104 $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ with n-type electrical conductivity. It can be doped as both n type and p-type semiconductor, which is unusual for the II-VI semiconductors (Saidi and Aisi, 2015).

Fig. (2.1): The schematic diagrams of a-orthorhombic structure of ZnS.

Thin Film

Thin film is a crystalline or non-crystalline material developed two dimensionally on a substrate surface by chemical or physical method (Eid *et al.*, 2010). It can also be defined as a layer of materials ranging from fractions of a nanometre to several micrometres in thickness (nanotechnology). They play a vital role in nearly all electronic and optical devices; they have been used as electroplated films for decoration and protection (Heaven, Thin films are less than 100nm thick made from dielectric transparent Materials and have refractive indices less than that of the substrate (Pentia *et al.*, 2014). It involves either chemical reaction at the substrate such as discharge of ions, decomposition of a compound, reaction of a gas or liquid with substrate surface or physical process such as evaporation from the source and sputtering from the target. Then condensation on a substrate surface (Elidrissi, 2019). They may also be formed from a solid, a paste or a gas. Examples

include: metallic films, semiconducting films and insulating films.

Benefits of Thin Films

Thin films are of great benefits, some of the benefits are:

- 1: They could be used to produce solar panels which in turn could be used to produce clean and quite electricity. Such alternative source of cheap electricity will reduce electricity bills, guard against rising energy cost, protect the environment and provide uninterrupted power supply
- 2: They are used as semiconductor in manufacturing equipment
- 3: They are also used in the production of transistors for large area electronics.

Types of thin films

1. Metallic films: The metallic films are deposited by thermal evaporation, sputtering and depositing method.

Metal films provide conducting and transparent barrier electrodes for various types of solar cells. When metallic vapour atoms are produced or formed by one of the above method arrive at the substrate, they may stick to the substrate or immediately re-evaporate, or may hop around the substrate until they come to thermal equilibrium (Dahy and Abou-Elkhair, 2018). The theory of nucleation predicts that films of large island structure will be produced when:

- a) The substrate temperature is high
- b) The activation of energy for surface diffusion is low (e.g. surface contaminated by absorbed gas)
- c) The film material has a low boiling point.
- d) The rate of deposition is low.
- e) The energy of absorption between the film and the substrate is low (Regragui *et al.*, 2019).

After the formation of critical nuclei, which may consist of less than ten atoms, further growth by capture of mobile absorbed atoms is more likely than dissociation. Growth also occurs by coalesce with other nuclei and eventually the nuclei become

sufficiently large to be visible by transmission electron microscope (Salim, 2015).

2. Dielectric or insulating films: Dielectric films are widely used as insulating layers between conductors, diffusion barriers and hardness coating for scratch and wear resistance. Dielectric films with a wide transmission range and low refractive index can also be used as anti-reflective coating to reduce the loss of light in lenses and mirrors. There are three basic methods of preparing dielectric films. These are evaporation, anodization and chemical bath deposition method.
3. Semiconducting films: These are used for integrated circuits, thin film transistors and solar cell etc. Most modern semiconductors include thin film as essential part for their operation e.g. insulated gate field effect transistors (Erken, 2017).

Methods Of Tin Film Deposition

There are several ways of thin film deposition. The methods range from very simple and cheap to complex and very expensive ones, depending on the substrate coating materials and on the required performance of the film (Ezema and Asogwa, 2017). However, thin film deposition is broadly divided into two (2): the physical deposition technique and the chemical deposition technique.

Physical deposition technique

This uses mechanical or thermodynamic means to produce a thin film. The material to be deposited is placed in an energetic, entropic environment so that the particles of the material escapes from its surface (Fang *et al.*, 2010). The source is faced with a cooler surface that draws the energy from the particles as they drive, allowing them to form solid layer. The whole system is kept in a vacuum chamber. Films deposited by physical deposition method and commonly directional rather than conformal. Physical

deposition techniques include; vacuum evaporation, sputtering and epitaxial deposition technique (Lee, 2017).

Epitaxial deposition

This is the growth of a single crystalline film on a single crystalline surface (Odo Eya, 2014). Epitaxial growth techniques include hot wall epitaxy, molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), Solid Phase Epitaxy (SPE). Epitaxial deposition is greatly affected by temperature; which depends on evaporation contamination deposition rate. Deposition rate is given by $(R \leq A \exp Q_d/K_b T_e)$,

Where

A = constant

Q_d = Activation energy of the surface

K_b = Boltzmann constant

T_e = Epitaxial temperature

It is complex, very expensive and undesirable for large scale production where cost effectiveness is of great importance.

Vacuum Deposition Method

It involves using resisting heating technique whereby a material is heated to a sufficiently high temperature. It evaporates to produce the desired vapour atoms. It involves a system with a known vacuum and residual gas. The vapour atoms transverse the medium and are made to condense on a substrate surface to form a thin film (Limei, 2017). The accessories for the vacuum system include; the vapour, source, shutters substrate, leather, a planetary system (for uniform deposition over large area), controllers for deposition rate and film thickness (Dennis Bade, 2014).

Sputtering

This is the kinetic ejection of atoms from the surface of a material (cathode or target) by a bombardment with energetic particles. The sputtered atoms condense to form a film. Sputtering process is energy intensive but it is best suited for deposition of adherent films of multi component materials of any kind (Liu, 2013). Sputtering process is limited at high deposition rate, because the high energy is converted to heat energy. Example of

sputtering Process includes; glow discharge sputtering, magnetron sputtering, refractive sputtering (Asogwa and Ekwealor, 2017). The sputtering process is characterized by the

Following:

1. The sputtering field (i.e. number of ejected atoms per incident ion).
2. The yield depends on the angle of incidence of the ion and increases as $(\cos \Theta)$ The yield displays an undulating behaviour with periodicity corresponding to the groups of the element of the periodic chart.
3. The energy of the ejected atom shows a maxwellian distribution with long tail towards higher energies (Mahamuni, 2019).

Chemical Deposition Technique

Here, a fluid precursor undergoes a chemical change at a solid surface, leaving a solid layer. Thin film formed by chemical deposition method tends to be conformal rather than directional. Chemical deposition method is divided into two; chemical vapour deposition and chemical solution deposition (Bendre and Leppert, 2019).

Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD)

This is a process whereby there is condensation of a compound from gaseous phase onto a substrate to produce a solid deposit. It involves exposing the substrate to one or several compounds. If the compounds are not in vapour phase, they are vaporized first; before they are made to flow on the substrate. CVD has been used to deposit a wide variety of films including insulators, conductors and ferrites (Maity, 2015).

Spray pyrolysis

This is used to deposit transparent films of oxide in 1910. It involves thermally stimulated reaction between clusters of an aqueous solution of soluble salt of the constituent atoms of the desired compound onto the substrate maintained at about 400°C using spray nozzle with the help of filter carrier gas at predetermined pressure

and flow rate. The spray deposited films are strongly adherent, mechanically hard, pin hole free and stable with time and temperature (Monroy, 2018). The growth rate of the film obtained by spray pyrolysis is determined by the following factor;

1. The topographical nature and the microstructure of the substrate.
2. The chemical nature and concentration of spray solution and its additives.

Chemical Solution Deposition Technique (CSD)

This uses a liquid precursor, usually a solution of organometallic powders dissolved in an organic solvent is a relatively inexpensive, simple deposition method that is able to produce stigmatically accurate crystalline phase (Omnes *et al.*, 2018).

Anodization

This is a method of obtaining mainly oxide films. It is dependent upon the migration of oxygen ions to the anode surface through a medium that usually water but may be of some other materials such as fused salt (Nagamani *et al.*, 2012). The choice of a particular paste composition is detected by the designed characteristics of the final product. A large number of conductor, resistor and dielectric composition are commercially available.

Electrodeposition

The deposition of bath consists of electrolyte that provides the ions required for the deposition and electrodes which serves as substrate. This uses the principle of electrolysis given by equation,

$$M = \frac{IEt}{f}$$

Where:

M= Mass of the substance deposited

I= Current in amperes

E= Chemical equivalent weight in grams of substance deposited

f=Faradays constant=96500

On dipping a metallic electrode in solution, a dynamic equilibrium of this form is gotten:

Where;

M = Atom of the metal

N = Level of ionization

The Chemical Bath Deposition(CBD)

This is the cheapest, simplest, economical and affordable method of depositing thin films. It has been termed as auto catalytic deposition or electroless or solution growth technique. This method is used to deposit conducting and non-conducting electrochemical processes in the absence of an external field (Nasir *et al.*, 2014). It exploits the fact that films can be deposited on substrates whether metallic and non-metallic by dipping them into solution baths containing metal salts. The metal ions and non-metallic ions which are present in the deposition solution react with other to form neutral compounds. These complex ions of the metal provide a controlled number of free ion according to equilibrium reaction of the form (Palmer, 2019).

Where A is the ligand which does not take part in the reaction M^{2+} is the metal ion. At a particular temperature, the concentration of the free metal ions is given by;

$$\frac{[M^{2+}][A]}{[M(A)^{2+}]} = K_d$$

Where K_d is known as complex ion.

Characteristics of Chemical Bath Deposition

The substrate (a glass slide) is inserted vertically at the centre of the reaction bath (beaker), which is stirred continuously with a stirrer, the composition of the reaction baths depends on the material to be deposited. Growth parameters like; pH, concentration, time and temperature can be varied to obtain a better result (Porada and Osiewska, 2018). For growth to occur, nucleation centres are first formed. The rate of deposition rises rapidly after nucleation until the rate of deposition equals the rate of dissolution. The growth kinetics depends on the concentration of ions, ion velocity, nucleation and growth processes of the inserted surface (Rogach *et al.*, 2016).

- **Complexing Agent**

Complexing agent helps to slow down the reaction in order to prevent spontaneous precipitation of the compound.

- **pH Value**

As pH increases i.e. addition of more OH^- . The concentration of free metal decreases, resulting in decrease in deposition rate and increase in terminal thickness. This occurs in the case where OH^- precipitates out the corresponding hydroxide ions leading to lower terminal thickness at the high pH value.

- **Substrate Effects**

Matching of lattice parameters and lattices of the deposited materials with those of the substrates increases the deposition rate and terminal thickness.

- **Temperature Effects**

As the temperature of the solution increases, the rate of deposition increases. The terminal thickness increases as the temperature increases because of super saturation from the dissociated ions (Saeed *et al.*, 2016). However, if the super saturation is very high, precipitation occurs as at terminal thickness decreases with temperature.

- **Doping**

This is the introducing of impurities in the starting in the starting chemicals to be incorporated into the film. The impurities must be able to form insoluble oxides under the same deposition condition. The ionic product of the oxide must be greater than the solubility product of the complex. In practice, only few dopants satisfy these conditions; the requirement of the [above conditions imply that the degree of the purity of the working chemicals is not so important factor in determining the purity of resulting film (Tittel, 2019)

Advantages of Chemical Bath Deposition

- Large application of films produced with little chemicals.
- Deposition of uniform films.
- Deposition of epitaxial layer with high perfection and purity.
- Easy doping through introduction of controlled amount of impurity.

- Simplicity.
- High deposition rate.
- Easy control of stoichiometry of the deposition compound.

Disadvantages of Chemical Bath Deposition

1. Poor understanding of the thermodynamics and reaction kinematics involved in the deposition.
2. Difficulty in the control of uniformity of the deposited film.
3. Often toxic or corrosive nature of the reactive gases used for deposition (Wang, 2014).

Annealing

Annealing is the study of a solid/metal at a certain temperature above the decrystallization phase followed by a gradual cooling process. When solid materials are annealed, some of its properties are affected in different ways. Annealing is of different types and they are as follows:

Recovery Annealing

Recovery annealing is an annealing process that attempt to partially restore the original grain structure of the material and still retain some of its properties unaffected (Behera *et al.*, 2020). This can be used to achieve durability of the material through soaking process, strength through strain hardening.

Stress Relieving Annealing

This is an annealing process by which material is heated below its austenite phase to reduce distortion or change in dimension which may occur during processing (Oliveira, 2020).

Full Annealing

This is an annealing process that soaks the material above the austenite phase, followed by gradual cooling. In general, annealing changes the structure of a material and alters its physical properties (Chopra, 2021).

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Description Of Deposition Techniques Used

The techniques for the synthesis of the thin films in this study is dual - solution growth and successive ionic layer absorption and reaction technique. These techniques are cost-effective, convenient and highly reproducible for preparation of thin films (Ndukwe, 1995). Several parameters will be experimentally varied to determine which condition most significantly affects the deposition of sulphide alloy thin films.

Solution Growth Technique

Solution growth technique relies on liquid precursors, often a solution of water with salt of the metal to be deposited. Some process is entirely driven by reagent in the solution. Solution growth technique is also known as chemical bath deposition (CBD) or electroless method. This technique makes use of the fact that thin films can be grown on substrates whether metallic or not by dipping the substrate into a bath containing metallic salts without applying external electric field (Ezema and Osuji, 2007). It also possesses a number of advantages such as low cost, low working temperature and easy coating of large surfaces, over other thin film deposition methods (Oriaku and Osuwa, 2008). Figure 3.1 shows a typical CBD set-up.

Semiconductor materials such as CdS and PbS are the most common materials grown using this technique. Mgbaja (2010) has grown CdS/PbS by this technique using a liquid chemical solution containing 2ml of 0.2M cadmium chloride and 5ml of 1M thiourea and 2.5ml of 1M of lead acetate and 3ml of 1M thiourea at bath temperature of 100°C.

Figure 3.1: Schematic diagram of chemical bath deposition (CBD).

Successive Ionic Layer Adsorption and Reaction Method

Successive ionic layer adsorption and reaction (SILAR) is relatively new and less investigated method for the deposition of metal chalcogenide thin films (Pathan and Lokhande, 2004). SILAR method was first recorded as being used in 1985 in a laboratory environment, with the name SILAR first used in scientific journals of the same year, according to the Indian Academy of Sciences. It is based on the immersion of substrate into separately placed anionic and cationic precursors and rinsing between every immersion in distilled water to avoid inhomogeneous precipitation (Daniel-Umeri, 2012).

This method is used to fabricate sulphide alloy thin films with different variations in annealing temperature and time, to produce different coatings for applications.

Apparatus Used for the Deposition

The apparatus used for the deposition are:

Deposition bath

Distilled water

Substrate holder/synthetic foam

Glass slides

Electronic scale

Petri dishes and clips

Spatula

Measuring cylinders

Glass beakers

Clinical syringes

Thermometers

Stirring glass rods

Ph meter

Temperature bath

Reagents:

- i. Tin Chloride
- ii. Thiourea
- iii. TEA
- iv. Ethanol
- v. Ammonia
- vi. HCL
- vii. KOH
- viii. Distilled water

Substrate Preparation

The substrates (glass slides) were degreased in HCL for two hours, washed in cold water with detergent and then rinsed with distilled water and allowed to drip dry in air. The degreased cleansed surface has the advantage of providing nucleation centres for the growth of the films, hence yielding adhesives and uniformly deposited films (Ezema, 2006).

Deposition of Sulphide Alloy Thin Films Using Dual Solution Synthesis (SGT AND SILAR)

In this research work, compounds were deposited using solution growth and SILAR technique. Sulphide alloy thin films (ZnS, SnS) were deposited using SILAR after which it is dipped into a bath of ZnS prepared by solution growth technique respectively. At the end, there were four basic deposited thin films using the two techniques with variations in annealing temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spectral And Solid State Properties Of SnS:ZnS Thin

This chapter represents the results of growth and characterizations of four samples of SnS:ZnS thin films deposited on glass substrate by chemical bath deposition technique. The variations in absorbance/transmittance and reflectance for varying annealing temperature at normal incidence wavelength ranges between 350nm - 700nm of the films were obtained. The thickness of the films was obtained. Table 4.1 below shows the identification of samples of SnS:ZnS thin

films with variations in annealing temperature.

Table 4.1: Identification of samples of SnS:ZnS thin films with variations in annealing Temperature.

BATH SAMPLE	ANNEALING TEMPERATURE (K)
T0	As grown sample
T2	473
T3	523
T4	373
T5	423

Figure 4.1: Absorbance spectra of SnS:ZnS thin film annealed at different temperature.

The Spectral Absorbance

Figure 4.1 shows the spectral absorbance value of chemical bath deposited SnS:ZnS thin films deposited and annealed at different temperatures of 473K, 523K, 373 and 423K. The as grown sample was used as reference for annealing temperature. The spectral absorbance of sample T2 annealed at 473K showed the maximum value of about 0.7, sample T3 annealed at 523K showed the maximum value of about 0.9, sample T4 annealed at 373K showed the maximum value of about 0.2 T5 annealed at 423 showed the maximum of 0.4, while the as grown sample T0 showed 0.95 all corresponding to the wavelength of range of 350nm - 700nm in the UV- VIS region of the electromagnetic spectrum. The result shows that the annealing temperature has a significant effect on the absorbance of

chemical bath deposited SnS:ZnS thin film. This makes them useful for window coating for those living in the hot climates like Nigeria in the sense that the radiation will be absorbed by such films and the inside is kept cool.

The Spectral Transmittance

Figure 4.2 shows the spectral transmittance value of chemical bath deposited SnS:ZnS thin films deposited and annealed at different temperatures of 473K, 523K, 373K and 423. The as grown sample was used as reference for annealing; temperature.

The spectral transmittance of sample T2 annealed at 473K showed the maximum value of about 24.0%, sample T3 annealed at 523K showed the maximum value of about 10.0% of sample T4 annealed at 373K showed the maximum value of about 70.0% T5 annealed at 423 showed the maximum value of 48.0%, while the as grown sample T0 showed 10.0% all corresponding to the wavelength of range of 350nm - 700nm in the UV- VIS region of the electromagnetic spectrum. The result shows that the annealing temperature has a significant effect on the transmittance of chemical bath deposited SnS:ZnS thin film. The transmittance showed that the films annealed, have greater transmittance in the region studied. The transmittance properties exhibited make the film good material for screening of the UV portion of the electromagnetic spectrum which is dangerous to human health and as well harmful to domestic animals. The film can be used for coating eye glass for protection from sunburn caused by UV radiations. (Asogwa, 2011)

Figure 4.2: Transmittance spectra of SnS:ZnS thin film annealed at different temperature.

4.3: Reflectance (R) of SnS:ZnS thin film annealed at different temperature.

The Reflectance (R)

Figure 4.3: Shows the Reflectance value of chemical bath deposited SnS:ZnS thin films deposited and annealed at different temperatures of 473K, 523K, 373K and 423. The as grown sample was used as reference for annealing; temperature.

The spectral transmittance of sample T2 annealed at 473K showed the maximum value of about 13.0%, sample T3 annealed at 523K showed the maximum value of about 5.0% of sample T4 annealed at 373K showed the maximum value of about 20.1% T5 annealed at 423 showed the maximum value of 20.0%, while the as grown sample T0 showed 10.0% all corresponding to the

wavelength of range of 350nm - 700nm in the UV-VIS region of the electromagnetic spectrum. The result shows that the annealing temperature has a significant effect on the transmittance of chemical bath deposited SnS:ZnS thin film. The transmittance showed that the films annealed, have greater transmittance in the region studied. The transmittance properties exhibited make the film good material for screening of the UV portion of the electromagnetic spectrum which is dangerous to human health and as well harmful to domestic animals. The film can be used for coating eye glass for protection from sunburn caused by UV radiations. (Asogwa, 2011)

Figure 4.3: Reflectance spectra of SnS:ZnS thin film annealed at different temperature.

Figure 4.4: Absorption coefficient spectra of SnS:ZnS thin film annealed at different temperature.

Figure 4.5: Extinction coefficient spectra of SnS:ZnS thin film annealed at different temperatures.

Figure 4.6: Refractive index spectra of SnS:ZnS thin film annealed at different temperatures.

Figure 4.7: $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus photon energy (eV) of SnS:ZnS thin film annealed at different temperatures.

Table 4.2: Values of maximum optical and solid state properties of chemical bath deposited SnS:ZnS thin films.

Bath Sample	Absorption Coefficient $\alpha_0 (\times 10^6) m^{-1}$	Band Gap E.g. (eV) ² m ⁻²	Extinction Coefficient (K)	Refractive Index (n)	Absorbance Spectra (A)	Transmittance Spectra T (%)	Reflectance Spectra R (%)
T0	1.60	0.00	58.0	1.780	1.91	4.0	5.0
T2	0.81	140.0	46.0	1.599	0.70	1.0	3.0
T3	1.50	130.0	56.0	1.710	0.85	1.0	5.0
T4	0.40	70.0	16.0	1.351	0.20	6.0	20.1
T5	0.50	80.0	26.0	1.399	0.38	40.0	20.0

The plot of the solid state properties including, energy band gap, extinction coefficient, refractive index, absorbance spectra, transmittance spectra and reflectance spectra against their corresponding photon energies are shown in figures 4.1-4.7 As contained in table 4.2, there are variations in the solid state properties of the chemical bath deposited glass/SnS:ZnS for different annealing temperature. The result shows that the annealing temperature has a significant effect on the transmittance of chemical bath deposited SnS:ZnS thin film.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The chemical bath deposition method employed for the growth of tin sulphide and zinc sulphide (SnS:ZnS) thin film was successful. The band gap of the film (3.5eV) suggested that the material is a semiconducting thin film.

The optical and solid state properties such as reflectance (R), absorbance e (A), transmittance (T), refractive index (n), extinction coefficient (K), Refractive index (n), Absorbance spectra (A), and Transmittance Spectra T (%) determined showed that the material could be used as:

1. Photovoltaic: In the fabrication of solar panels.
2. Automobile: In car industry such as anti-dazzling on the window screen.
3. Architectural design to reduce exposure to skin cancer, cataracts and the impaired immune -system due to UV rays.
4. In agricultural industry, to reduce greenhouse effect

RECOMMENDATION

Bearing in mind that there is no research work that is the final, the following suggestions and recommendations for more research work are listed.

1. Since this material has high transmittance and capable of absorbing UV rays, urgent development of this technology is recommended to lenses and mirror manufacturers. Also to environmental experts to reduce dangers of UV ray.
2. It is recommended that the other methods of deposition such as physical vapour deposition (sputtering) etc should be used. The result obtained will be compared with the results of this work.
3. Testing of new combination of semi conducting materials and electrolyte-solvent systems.
4. Development of assembling technologies.
5. The effect of using other complexing agents like

nitrilotriacetate (NTA) and cychohexane diamonetriracetate(CDTA) should be looked into by researchers.

Finally, a crystal growth and characterization laboratory is recommended to be established for the department of physics, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, where some of this basic equipment's can be accessed. This will increase researchers interest in doing research work in this area.

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